

DISCUS PROJECT 21470018

RESEARCH STUDY

RECOMMENDATION ON IMPLEMENTATION OF RELEVANT INFORMATION SYSTEM FOR LOCAL AUTHORITIES

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Abbreviations

BR	- Basic Registries
DISCUS	- Discussion on Information Society Building Issues Platform
EDIFACT	- Electronic Data Interchange For Administration Commerce and Transport
EGON	- System of the Shared Services in the Czech Republic
ICT	- Information & Communication Technologies
IS	- Information System
ISDI/IDSI	- Information Society Development Institute, Moldova
ISPA	- Information System of Public Administration in Czech Republic
LCMS	- Learning Content Management System - Content Management System for Training
LLL	- Life-Long Learning
LMS	- Learning Management System
PA	- Public Administration
PIAPs	- Public Internet Access Point
PPP	- Public-private Partnership
PRINCE2	- Projects In a Controlled Environment is a project management method based on a process approach
PuP	- Public-public partnership is a partnership between government administration or other public authority or other body eg
SOA	- Service Oriented Infrastructure
V4	- Visegrad countries: Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, Slovakia

1. Introduction

The present research study “Recommendation on implementation of relevant information systems for local authorities” is written within the DISCUS project as the result of the 1st project event, Workshop: ICT-driven local development, held in Chisinau on March 17-18, 2015.

During the last years information society issues became a central subject for discussions for Moldovan Government and other key-actors (business, civil society, research and education sector etc.). The DISCUS Project platform is offering an excellent opportunity for all actors to discuss these issues with partners from Visegrad countries. The project "DISCUSSION on Information Society Building Issues Platform" aims at promoting the European model of effective application of information society policies/e-Governance tools in Moldova to strengthen participation of academic sector, local government, business, civil society, mass-media in decision making process, using the experience of V4 countries. The goal of this study is to analyse the lessons learned by the participating countries and to develop a set of recommendations, which will enable the digitisation of services delivered to citizens by the local public authorities.

Country context – Republic of Moldova

In the Republic of Moldova the main necessary legislative and normative framework was created for building information society. It currently includes more than 20 laws, 80 Government decisions, about 70 approved conceptual documents regarding the information systems of public authorities, more than 20 general purpose regulatory acts and 75 with a specific purpose issued by ANRCETI. The relevant institutional framework is in place which includes the Ministry of Information Technology and Communications, The National Regulatory Agency for Electronic Communications and Information Technology (ANRCETI), National Radio Frequency Center, Center for Electronic Governance and National Center for Personal Data Protection.

Strategic Program for Governance Technological Modernization (e-Transformation), supported by the World Bank, was adopted in 2011. In 2013 the National Strategy “Digital Moldova 2020” was approved by the Government and is being implemented. Recently, the Government approved a package of initiatives to increase the competitiveness of the IT industry: the draft Strategy for the years 2015-2020 and the draft Law on information technology industry parks, aimed at creating the necessary prerequisites for boosting development of the information technology industry oriented towards export.

The e-Governance Center is the institution responsible on behalf of the Government for the implementation of the e-Transformation Agenda and set up an unique platform for public services provided by the central authorities - <http://www.servicii.gov.md> portal. This platform functions as an electronic catalogue for public services provided by the authorities dedicated to citizens and the business. The main purpose of this platform is to offer brief, correct, accessible and complete information on the public services available in the Republic of Moldova.

On the platform, you can find information regarding both electronic services, as well as traditional services. The visitors can find the description of the services, the set of documents required for this services, the schedule of the services, the costs and the implementation duration. They can also find contact details for more information and the forms that have to be completed by the citizens in electronic format, including completion's guidance.

The platform is divided into service categories for:

- Citizens (information and petition, finance and taxes, licences and special permits, etc.)
- Businesses (taxes, reports, confirming acts, permissive acts, etc.)
- Visitors (Moldovan citizenship, entry and stay in the Republic of Moldova)
- Life scenarios (emigration, immigration, business initiation, real estate, creating a family, health, studies)

Currently, there are 248 services on the portal, of which 13 are e-Services (on-line services) with data opened for access. The Republic of Moldova Government is determined to transform all traditional counter services into e-services by 2020, through the „Open Government action plan” and the „Government technological modernisation strategy”. In this way, the citizens will be able to access over 500 e-services.

However, the speed of e-Transformation agenda implementation is not yet at the necessary level. Moreover, a substantial gap exists between the level of services offered at the central level and those offered at the local level. Therefore the discussion platform offered by DISCUS project on ICT-driven local development, aimed to identify relevant issues and enhance local participation in the decision-making process could help in strengthening the capacities of local authorities on the one hand and in involvement of central public authorities, academic sector and civil society in discussion of LPA problems on the other hand.

On March 17-18, 2015 the first event of the DISCUS project, workshop “ICT-driven local development” was held in Chisinau (Agenda attached in Annexes). The event was attended by more than 55 participants, representatives of different sectors: academic sector, governmental sector, Visegrad countries' diplomatic corps, civil society, mass-media.

The main goal of the event was to share the Visegrad countries experience in information society field with focus on local e-services as well as raise awareness on the importance of the local e-services by the Moldovan public servants and other relevant stakeholders.

The Report is based on:

- Approved DISCUS Project Document,
- TOR provisions,
- Experts’ own experience on best practices in Czech Republic, Poland and Slovakia on ICT driven local development,
- Analysed V4/EU countries experience/initiatives relevant to the DISCUS project objectives,
- Analysis of presented information and discussions during the Workshop,
- Analysis of issues, solutions, plans proposed by the local authorities representatives expressed in working groups,
- Analysis of ideas expressed during informal communications.

Participants to the event opening: dr. Igor Cojocaru - director of the Information Society Development Institute, dr.hab. Veaceslav Ursachi - the representative of the Academy of Sciences of Moldova, Mr. Pavel Şincariuc - the head of the Department of Information Technology Policies of the [Ministry of ICT](#), Mr. Peter Tomasek - the representative of the Slovak Embassy in Chisinau.

The key-speakers of the event were 3 experts from Visegrad countries: dr. Krzysztof Atlasiewicz (Poland); Ing. Vladimir Benko (Slovakia); RN Dr. Datel Vratislav (Czech Republic). The experts talked about the experience in local e-services field exemplifying both best practices and lessons learned, finally formulating a range of useful tips and recommendations.

Local key speakers: Ms. Cornelia Amihalachioae (Center for Electronic Governance) - talked about the Governance e-Transformation, the results and priorities of this process in Moldova; Ms. Olesia Cazacu (Joint Integrated Local Development Programme, UNDP Moldova) presented data and results of the Study on access and usage prospects of local public services on-line; Ms. Veronica Creţu (president of the Open Government Institute and member of the steering committee of the Open Government Partnership) had a presentation about Local Open Government based on ICT tools; Mr. Igor Plamadeala (Ialoveni LPA) presented the study case of the Ialoveni Rayon/district on Electronic Document Management System Implementation; Mr. Ion Cosuleanu (IDSi) presented the new project on e-Competence Centres “Look@IT” - a new initiative on creation of opportunities in IT for young people in rural area.

The practical workshop on local e-services resulted in identification of priority (most necessary) services to be implemented at local level (cadastral e-services, archive services, educational and health services etc.).

DISCUS workshop participants showed interest regarding the subject of local electronic services and awareness on the importance of technology in all areas of public life.

Conclusions

Republic of Moldova has made significant progress in the digitization of public services at the central level. The success of these activities creates promising prerequisites for the digitisation of the local public services, by providing access to registries and databases of central authorities, by transfer of experience, by adapting existing technical solutions to the specific local context.

However, at the moment, a consolidated vision on local public services that could be digitized, as well as future institutional framework, to ensure their digitization, don't exist.

2. Visegrad countries experience in ICT driven local development and best practices relevant to be approached by Moldova

2.1 Czech Republic experience

The aspiration to machine processing of the administrative information, especially for processing of the text information in the Czech Republic has started to be shown on the turn of the 80s-90s.

This aspiration has been supported by the Federal Statistical Office of the Federal Ministry of Finance issuing the Regulation No. 173/1980 Col. „About the unified base of facts on organisations”.

At the global level, in 1981 in Prague have begun works on the standard EDIFACT - (Electronic Data Interchange For Administration Commerce and Transport).

The first computers for processing of the text information (TEXT01, 8-bit) in Czech language have appeared in 1983.

In parallel with works on standards, several qualifiers have been published:

- Unified classification of employment
- Unified classification of field of study and teaching professions
- Unified classification of practice of profession
- Unified classification of business
- Unified classification of countries
- Unified classification of organizations
- Spatial identification of information (regions, districts)
- Unified classification of unit of measuring and economical units
- Unified categorization of basic means of production

Based on these qualifiers, catalogues of the unified elements of the data have been developed, published and introduced:

- The basic characteristics of the person (1981)
- Definitions and qualifiers from areas of work, salaries and social affairs (1980)
- Area - characteristics of the general nature (1981)
- and the following (Transport, Building, Education, ...)

After the edition and introduction of standards ISO 7372 Processes, data elements and documents in commerce, industry and administration (1986), ISO 9735 Electronic data interchange for administration, commerce and transport (EDIFACT) -- Application level syntax rules (1987), it was possible to create the unified base of elements of the data for trade, persons and social affairs.

All these works at the global level have led ISO to begin works on the standard ISO 11179 Specification and normalisation of data elements (1991).

During 1987-2006 four databases of the unified data elements have been set up in the Czech Republic. Two databases at ministerial level:

- ISC MÚZO at Ministry of foreign trade, full implementation ISO 7372, (1987)
 - Personnel department of the Ministry of Defence (1990),
- and two databases at the state level:
- Ministry of Defence (1997)
 - Ministry of Interior (13.04. 2006) (<https://www.sluzby-isvs.cz>)

Both systems are developed based on full implementation of the ISO/IEC 11179 and are in operation.

These tools together with the published regulations (for example Regulation of the Ministry of the Informatics CR No. 469/2006 Col. „On Information system about data elements” and subsequent) have created conditions for system engineering for granting not only electronic services, but first of all for **integrability** of information systems generally, not only information systems of public administration.

For the introduction of electronic services it was necessary to accept a number of regulations and laws. Three groups of laws and regulations were approved:

- The first group: Law No. 365/2000 Col. „About information systems of public management” and subsequent,
- The second group: Law No. 499/2004 Col. „About archival business and office-work” and subsequent.
- The third group: Law No. 300/2008 Col. „About electronic certificates, personal numbers and the authorised converting of documents” and subsequent.

Acceptance of these three groups of laws and regulations has opened a way to digitisation of public administration, including the implementation of electronic services not only for the population, but first of all for the whole public area, based on the slogan: **“the data, and not the citizen, must be circulated”**.

The basic components of an information system in public administration are:

Basic registries - as central information source for information systems of public authorities. In addition, basic registries are a central hub for interchange of additional information, related to information, stored in basic registers – e. g. Information System (IS) of vehicles, IS of drivers, IS of foreigners etc. Basic Registries (BR) include:

- BR of Inhabitants – holds the data of inhabitants;
- BR of Persons – holds the data on companies and governmental agencies;
- BR of Territorial identification, addresses and real estates – holds the data on buildings;
- BR of Rights and responsibilities – holds the data about administrative decisions.

Operational status

- Start 1. 07. 2012.
- Over 463 mil. transactions since 1st of July 2012.
- Over 2 529 public authorities connected.
- Over 3 613 IS of public authorities connected.

EGON - System of the Shared Services in the Czech Republic. EGON consists of:

- Communications infrastructure including CMS (central interconnect)
- Basic registries: (People, Companies, Land and Houses, Rights a Duties)
- Databoxes
- CzechPOINT
- Governmental portal
- List of OVM (Register of offices)
- JIP/KAAS – unified identity space for public servants

This system is intended for providing electronics services on regional and local levels.

Regional services:

- Regional networks interconnect
- Regional shared services centers
- Public services digital map
- Document management.

Local services:

- Statutory cities shared services centers
- Cities shared services centers
- CzechPOINTS front offices
- Public services digital map
- Document management.

Operational status:

- Started 1.10.2007
- Total number of exits 12. 836 805 as of 22.04.2015.

These services are provided through more than 7100 offices of CzechPOINT on the whole territory of the Czech Republic.

For more details, see presentation.

(http://www.discus.idsi.md/sites/default/files/Methodological_approach_ICT-driven_local_development-Datel.V.pdf)

2.2. Poland experience

Best practices in ICT driven development include:

1. Investment in infrastructure
2. Avoidance of Digital Divide,
3. Private-Public Partnerships,
4. Public-Public Partnerships,
5. Keeping the systems Open,
6. Life-Long Learning,
7. Smart Cities.

1) Investment in infrastructure

Network and telecommunications infrastructure is essential for provision of telecommunications services. It includes wires, optical fibers, masts, wells, nodes, collocation points, cabinets, containers, locations for systems radio or intended for them towers and masts etc. Thanks to this infrastructure, residents, businesses and public sector entities will be able to access the modern broadband telecommunications services, applications and information resources available on the network in areas where there is no such ability or the lack of competition does not provide any choice or a satisfactory quality of services.

Other important aspect of infrastructure are PIAPs (Public Internet Access Point):

- external and internal kiosks,
- telecentres – PC in specially designated areas,
- hot-spots - access devices for Internet signal separation.

From the public administration point of view it is also very important to provide modern data centers, either as a building or a room for storing operating infrastructure: servers, data storage devices (storage) and network infrastructure. Data centers must contain not only computers, but also mechanisms and procedures to enhance the security and continuity of servers, such as server redundancy, network components and drives, ventilation and cooling systems, fire protection and access control.

2) Avoidance of Digital Divide

The development of Information Society may be threatened by the digital divide - the division of society into those with access to the Internet and modern forms of communication, as well as those without such opportunities. It results with the rapid development of information technology, which led to the enlargement of differences between the rich and the average class,

that could afford to buy them, and the underclass, which can not afford to have free access to the Internet. Currently, you can not even talk about the new kind of social stratification, where the division is between connected and unconnected to the network. The term digital divide is not simply the ability to access the Internet, in addition are important factors such as:

- Internet skills,
- quality of the connection,
- linguistic dimension (lack of knowledge of the language in which the necessary information is presented).

Thus it is very important to have projects, with the objective to provide free Internet access and the necessary hardware and software to the households, as well as proper training. Such projects minimize the risk of exclusion from active participation in the information society, due to the difficult financial situation or disability.

3) Private-Public Partnerships

Public-private partnership (PPP) is a form of cooperation between government entities and local government (public administration) and private entities in the sphere of public services. The partnership may include areas such as e.g. construction of apartments for rent, sports and recreation centers, parks, schools, offices of public authorities or public utilities, as well as the construction of roads and highways, ports and airports.

However PPP may be also used in IT projects. There are several types of PPPs that may be utilized:

- Operation and maintenance,
- Design and construction,
- Design, construction and operation,
- Design, construction, financing and operation.

Cooperation within the PPP leads to maximizing the benefits of the public sector and the social objective, which is to meet the needs of the collective. For the private partner, in turn, aims to achieve the effect of a commercial, or return on investment. Public entity initiating the investment, should be guided by the principle of "value for money", i.e. obtaining the greatest possible benefit to society. As such the use of PPPs for the project should take place when the realization of such a project is more favorable than the implementation of the traditional method.

It should be clearly noted that the public-private partnership improves the quality of ongoing infrastructure projects and provided services. It is important that the choice of mode of PPP have similar or only slightly higher costs than those using traditional solutions, such as public procurement. It is expected that the PPP in Poland will be the increasingly used method of satisfying social needs. Increasingly noticeable are the practical aspects of the use of this mode of implementation of the infrastructure or the provision of services by public entities, which in the near future, it should turn into a creation of a kind of code of good practice.

4) Public-Public Partnerships

Public-public partnership (PuP) is a partnership between government administration or other public authority and another body e.g. non-profit organization to provide services or facilities, sometimes in order to transfer technical skills and expertise in international development projects. Partners can be local, regional, state, provincial, tribal, minority governments, national governments and federal, school boards, board parks, NGOs, trade unions, pension funds, professional associations, and governments, labor organizations, NGOs and local communities in developing countries.

Public-public partnership is opposed to public-private Partnership (PPP). PPP contracts include its operation between the government and corporations to design, build, finance, maintain and manage public services such as e.g. schools, hospitals and bridges. In recent decades, PPP participants experienced a large global corporations. PuPs can be applied to IT development.

5) Keeping the systems Open

There are two main aspects of keeping IT open:

Interoperability -The initiative to create and encourage suppliers to use the system of standards, protocols and recommendations, which in turn facilitates the work of the common perception of computer systems or integrating them visible from the perspective of the end user.

Openness - the condition that the network built in the framework of the project will be open to all users (operators) who would like to use them on an equal footing. This condition affects the organizational principles and engineering. Condition of openness will be provided by such planned infrastructure to be able to handle multiple operators and by ensuring a level playing field access to this infrastructure, sharing rooms collocation space. On the technical side, openness provides network architecture, standardized interfaces, Specifications and availability in all areas covered by the project. Openness of network must be provided not only by the planning of appropriate solutions, but it is also a contractual obligation of infrastructure operator (the entity managing the infrastructure and services in the network) ensuring equal treatment of operators using its network.

It is very important to ensure that those two conditions are met. Otherwise it is very difficult to assure proper data exchange. The other aspect of lack of open systems is the growing cost of it. Lack of openness equals less competitive IT market.

6) Life-Long Learning

Another very important concept to implement is Lifelong Learning Programme (LLL). This concept underlines the need for constant change in the market requirements. This is particularly important in IT development, since there is a constant progress in technology and human resources have to adapt.

There are several initiatives that can help the concept of LLL:

- Digital Repository: place of orderly storage of digital documents, graphics, files.
- Digital library: a service that enables network sharing digital publications, such as magazines or electronic books, as well as digitized traditional paper publications (magazines, books, maps, photographs, etc.).
- LMS - Learning Management System. The main task of LMS is to help in the management of the training activity. LMS manages access to online courses for which the user has been registered. LMS facilitates the tracking, management and reporting of training activities in the organization.
- LCMS - Learning Content Management System - Content Management System for Training. LCMS helps to create, use, locate, deliver, manage, and improve the content of training.

There is a program of the European Union in the field of education and training. The program continues the activities carried out before programs Socrates, Leonardo da Vinci, Jean Monnet, e-Learning and the European Language Label. The aim of the program is to develop various forms of learning throughout life by supporting cooperation between education and training systems in the participating countries. The program is to contribute to improving the quality and increase the attractiveness of vocational education and training in Europe.

7) Smart Cities

Smart City is a concept of city, which uses ICT to increase the interactivity and performance of urban infrastructure and its constituent components, as well as to raise awareness of the inhabitants. This part of the definition draws attention to the role of mostly widely understood technologies. The city can be regarded as "smart" when making investment in human and social capital and the communication infrastructure in order to actively promote sustainable economic development and quality of life, including the wise management of natural resources, through civic participation.

Massachusetts Institute of Technology defines this concept as intelligence combined comprised of more efficient digital telecommunications networks (compared to the nerves), ubiquitously present intelligence (compared to the brain), sensors and tags (compared to the organs of the senses) and software (compared to the knowledge and cognitive competence). Intelligence does not exist in isolation from other urban systems. There is a growing network of

overlapping calls to the mechanical and electrical systems, existing buildings, embedded in household appliances, transportation systems, electrical networks, the network of water supply and sewage removal and systems that ensure the safety of the urban population.

One of the smart city concepts is urban card:

- contactless MIFARE card able to communicate with other devices and
- card on smartphones as mobile application.

The card helps residents facilitate the use of public transport journeys subscription, and in later stages of the project is also to perform for her with other measures.

2.3. Slovakia experience

The competences of public administration (PA) in Slovakia are divided between state administration (national level – ministries and districts, a total number of 79) and self-government (created by 8 self-governed regions and 2890 cities and villages). All together these are generating information and providing services. The target is to transform these services in e-Services. It means all institutions are involved in building and operating e-Gov services, for about 5.4 millions of inhabitants living on an area of 49.000 square kilometres.

The institutions of PA historically built their own information systems (IS) without coordination. Essential change and the start of systematic building of IS came after adoption of law 261/1995 about the state information system. Based on the law, ministries started developing conceptions of ministerial IS and the state budget allocated specific subsidies for building the infrastructure and partially the IS.

The central coordination of building state IS started later, after adoption of new **law 275/2006 on information systems of public administration (ISPA)**. Based on this law, in 2008 the **Strategy of informatics of PA** was developed and adopted and in the same year the **National Conception of Informatics of PA (NCIPA)** was developed. NCIPA set the architecture and principles and is valid till today. All ministries had to develop their own conceptions of extensions for the ministerial information systems in line with NCIPA, for the period 2008 – 2013. It was forbidden to build modules in ministries, which were under the responsibility of the central system and the ministries had to use the central modules. This process was supported by allocation of funding. Work improvement started after the preparation of a dedicated Operational Program (Operational Program of Informatics of Society = OPIS) for the period 2007-2013, with the possibility to use the resources till the end of 2015. OPIS allocated resources of about 1000 million Euro. Feasibility Studies were compulsory before the preparation of project applications for development of IS, financed from OPIS. They consistently identified relevant e-Services for citizens, entrepreneurs and PA itself, which was the pre-condition for financial support from OPIS.

Single components of ISPA architecture were built according to the valid national conception (NCIPA). But e-Gov building wasn't supervised on the central state level, therefore whole systems and single components were built in a non-harmonized way, which caused many problems and delays. Only in last 3 years, we started supervising the e-Gov building more consistently, but it was very complicated, due to existing contracts, spent resources and various states of single IS development.

It is obvious from this story, that **building of e-Gov must be strongly supervised** and requires a thorough preparedness – administrative tools (legal regulations, standards, national conception and architecture, decomposition of whole system to partial projects verified by feasibility studies), qualified and trained personnel and set rights for supervisors and adequate financial resources.

In Slovakia, e-Gov building started at the national level and only 2 years prior the end of the programme period (in 2012), projects for regional self-government units (8 regions) and project DCOM (DataCenter of Villages and Cities) for systematic support of local governments,

were initiated. This way we are building and financing e-Government by top-down methods, because of many similar components and pre-condition for local e-Services.

In the meantime the cities and some villages developed useful partial IS/e-Services or provided information services for citizens through their own websites, some of them successfully involving the public into decision-making processes on the local level. Many developed information systems at city level were cheaper than others, built at central level, public awareness was increased, as well as clerks’ skills. One weakness of these IS is low quality of data or no regular actualization.

Based on this experience we believe **systematic approach is important** and building of local services must use good quality data and share data of other state institutions. Harmonization of central and local e-Gov levels takes time. Besides technical problems, there are also changes in regulations and state institution competencies, which leads to changes in IS.

As mentioned, NCIPA meant a big step forward in building e-Gov in Slovakia. It set up architecture, IS structure, components, legislation, supervision, broadband development, relations between relevant parts and target groups with their own various tasks. It was not easy, not without mistakes, not cheap, but these lectures are important for proper development of information society and active participation in the digital world.

The general scheme of the typical IS including the surrounding environment of users on national and European levels is presented in the picture below.

The architecture of Public Administration (PA) IS on the national level was set as follows:

Common modules of the PA Central Portal (national portal):

- Identity and Access Management
- Payment Module

- eDesk Module – evidence of communication inputs/outputs, eBoxes,
- Module of Notifications
- Module of eDelivery
- eForm Module
- Module of the Central Registry – point of incoming and outgoing messages
- Module of Longtime Deposit of e-Docs

The Basic Access Components

- PA Central Portal
 - Integrated Support Center
 - Call Center
- Components** on national level
- Electronic Identity Card - eID
 - Basic Identifiers
 - Basic Registers and Source Registers
 - Basic Classifiers
 - Basic Standards
 - Other Components
 - Metainformation system
 - Portal of public servants
 - Register of public institutions – with competences
 - Module of G2G Documents Exchange

Communication Infrastructure

Information Systems of Sectors of State Government with typical structure:

- Sector Portal with eServices – interconnected with central Portal
- Sectorial Metainformation System
- Partial Information Systems of Sector
- Sectorial Registries, Classifiers and Standards

Communication between systems or modules is ensured based on **Service Oriented Architecture (SOA)**, which is important for interconnection of information systems, online access to actual data and easier change management. Well proposed and developed information systems with high level of interoperability are basis for the final stage – functioning and reliable e-Services for clients. The aim is to build information systems of level 5. But lower levels are the way for digital success in e-Government services.

As a summary, the main building blocks of good information systems – both important on national as well as local level – are:

- Systematic approach and good management
- Links between legislation, infrastructure and digital content of agendas, which are continuously under development and improvement
- Building of information systems based on Competencies of authorities (national, regional, local) / (public, governmental, self-governed) based on legislation

- National ICT architecture using set/built components
- Well managed access rights, authorization and authentication of users
- Open non-platform binding access for end users
- User friendly front-end
- Safe, Secure and Reliable, 24/7/365 operated systems and services
- Back-office people (IT and on subject of IS/e-Services oriented) with tasks to manage, operate, update systems and help users
- Training modules for operators, as well as for users (e.g. eLearning)
- Well managed time frame of building IS/e-Services in the republic and its mutual linkages, as well as taking into account local level developments
- Never ending system of updates in line with changes of legislation, local conditions, ICT changes, other IS/e-Services changes, ...
- Sustainability

Correct management of building and implementing IS is of utmost importance. Below is an example of implementation units structure, where the titles suggest the tasks for experts:

2.4. Conclusions

Based on the experience of Visegrad countries, it can be ascertained that the digitization of local services was initiated based primarily on the degree of demand for these services, while the informational support relies, primarily on centralized resources.

The legal-normative framework has a key role in the digitization of local public services, in the absence thereof, the services that could be provided in electronic form become mainly information services for the citizens.

An importing role in facilitating the digitization of public services was played by the standardization of public services, which allowed increasing their accessibility and reducing costs for development and implementation of a proper information infrastructure.

The digitization of local public services in Visegrad countries became possible due to extensive digital literacy campaigns of the population, especially the elderly.

Clearing the digital divide between urban and rural environments is a necessary condition for successful implementation of digital services provided by local authorities.

3. Lessons learnt: ICT-driven local development

3.1. Czech Republic experience

Successful creation and introduction of Information System of Public Administration (ISPA) at local level (region, district) is not possible without:

1. Creation of the legislative and normative uniform environment for all ISPA.
2. Creation of the Information system about data elements for:
 - working out not only of all ISPA,
 - creation of conditions for integrability of ISPA at all levels of PA.
3. Creation of a methodology for every ISPA, as base for software development.

All experiences to bypass the above-stated positions by working out ISPA at state level or ministerial level or local level have ended with a failure (Czech Republic 1994, Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs 1995, Ministry of Defence 1996 and the following). It concerns also some IS at state level, which are not ISPA (e.g. IS of vehicles 2014).

When these basic conditions are not respected and implemented, there are big losses of resources (big money, lost time, labour).

3.2. Poland experience

Lesson learnt in ICT-driven local development include:

1. Proper User Requirement Analysis is a must
2. Proper Project Management ensures the success
3. Information is an asset - protect it
4. Keep solutions simple
5. Maintain your documentation

1) Proper User Requirement Analysis is a must

Functional requirements analysis allows to identify and describe the desired behavior of the system. Detailed functional requirements must describe the capabilities of the system in terms of behavior and the available operations (operations performed by the system response to user actions).

Functional requirements should describe :

- how the system is achieving its objectives and business performance within a given field,
- what conditions must be met in order for the system to perform certain tasks,
- how you will be able to use the system to perform certain tasks (which application module provides specific functionality, what steps you must follow in order to achieve a given result).

In certain cases (e.g. if the requirements are few and easy to manage) it is not necessary to run the full documentation requirements - list (catalog) requirements with reference to detailed documentation is telling enough.

Proper User Requirements Analysis ensures that the system meets people needs.

2) Proper Project Management ensures the success

One of the main issues that cause projects to fail is lack of project management. The methodology of the project should use elements of recognized standards in the field of project management such as PRINCE2 and PMBOK.

PRINCE2 (Projects In a Controlled Environment) is a project management method based on a process approach. Was developed by the Office of Government Commerce, United Kingdom, was first published it in 1996. The characteristics of this method are: to examine the business case design, precise definition of the project's products and a well-defined organizational structure and the division of the project into phases and tasks. This method

includes well-developed management techniques: risk, quality, changes and configurations. It is a standard in the UK and is gaining popularity in Europe.

The equivalent of the British standard in the US is the method PMBOK (A Guide to the Project Management Body of Knowledge), developed by the Project Management Institute. It is characterized by a holistic approach to the issue of project management and also includes project management areas such as: human resources management, tendering and contracting management, communication management etc.

3) Information is an asset - protect it

Building IS one has to remember that information is a valuable asset that has to be protected.

Security is preservation of:

- confidentiality,
- integrity and
- availability of information.

Note: In addition, other properties, such as authenticity, accountability, non-repudiation and reliability can also be involved." (ISO/IEC 27000:2009)

It is very important to include security issues from the start, because implementing it later could be costly.

4) Keep solutions simple

Occam's razor, also called the principle of economy or the principle of economy of thinking – is a principle, according to which in the explanation of phenomena one should strive for simplicity, choosing such explanations, which are based on a minimum number of assumptions and concepts.

This principle can be applied to IT. The architecture of a typical system resembles a patchwork. It is a consequence of several years of practice of systems implementation. The project is characterized by a cycle: first the need, then the system analysis, architecture design, system performance, testing and finally start. Users prefer integrated solutions, i.e. one supplier provides a set of hardware, operating system, platform and sometimes even their own archiving system, authentication methods, training and system privileges. Everything remains closed within a single application, called silo.

Then the system goes into operation and improvements: new functionality to earn some extra money here, there to ensure compliance with the amended provisions elsewhere modify or print reports etc. Before the implementation there is a need for integration. The easiest way to do so is to earn some extra data exchange interfaces. Each system implemented improvement leads to an exponentially growing number of interfaces. The result is a so called „spaghetti architecture” or system, wherein the modification of one component causes a lot of hard-to-determine consequences, such as pulling out one thread of pasta with spaghetti causes movement of the whole dish.

Part of the solution would be (and often is) a change in the architecture for services-based (SOA - Service Oriented Architecture), organizing communication between systems, but this change usually encounters problems. First, the communication bus itself is a new system and requires implementation. Secondly, the need for substantial modifications of the base systems (they do not communicate directly, but through the platform and its services). Thirdly, and most importantly, in the short term, such a change does not provide direct business benefits, measured as an increase or decrease in the cost of sales, so it is difficult to obtain a sponsor within the organisation for an expensive investment.

That is why the proper design, as well as optimizations, are so important.

5) Maintain your documentation

Keeping documentation right is a very important issue. It allows new people to learn the systems details. Here are some examples of proper documentation.

Project documentation

1) The design documentation must be coherent and co-ordinated in all areas associated with the execution of the contract and made in such form and at such a level of detail to allow its evaluation by another independent entity, it must include:

- a) processes directing project,
- b) the structure and content of the project plans,
- c) project management techniques,
- d) a set of controls and quality management.

System Documentation

1) System documentation must include:

- a) the introduction describing the objectives and scope
- b) restrictions solutions
- c) assumptions and dependencies
- d) the general characteristics of the users
- e) a description of the functional and non-functional requirements
- f) a description of the hardware and software requirements
- g) the description and specification of interfaces
- h) the progress of the testing program and the method used to estimate the reliability of the solution, including a proposal to test reports
- i) source code (as long as they produced the project) or supplied with the software.

2) The system documentation must fully reflect the architecture of the system, its organization and all the functions provided by the system to perform, as well as administrators and users.

3) The system documentation must specify the rules and plans for installation, commissioning and implementation of the system.

4) The documentation must specify the type of system, rules and acceptance test plan reception system along with their acceptance criteria, and procedures for testing.

5) A documentation system must indicate the critical points and threats affecting the reliable operation of the system.

Operating documentation

1) Operating documentation must contain at least the following:

- a) administrative procedures,
- b) security procedures (backup)
- c) emergency procedures
- d) procedures for the user.

3.3. Slovakia experience

IS users, both on government and clients sides, are an important element. As they are **end users** of the built information systems, it is necessary to think of **their needs** and involve them in the entire IS development process, including the phases of:

- analysis
- design
- testing
- pilot operation
- trainings
- awareness.

„Small” practical developments, experiences and user knowledge before setting up the robust information systems are important. Various motivation methods can be used, but less theory is preferable, with a focus on practical aspects, good examples and sharing of

experiences. It can move things forward and contribute to a well developed and well used information system.

It is important to build a **good attitude** of users to **quality of data, systematic work, partner's relationship** between users on both sides (government and citizens/entrepreneurs), **publication of information** as normal daily work, **pro-active work** and **engagement of public** in the decision making processes. Tools helping to visualize data or information can improve the work, e.g. using charts instead of big tables, using structured text instead of long articles or using Geographical information systems (GIS) which can combine information and visualize them on the map, with possibility to use also advanced functionalities of GIS for better benefit of users.

But of utmost importance is the **content** – users reading information on the web must find actual, updated information. When we stop updating information on the website when a project is finished, it is signal for the users to not visit the site anymore. This simple error leads to losing previous hours of engaging the users. Therefore the **sustainability** of systems, both from technical and content points of view is very important and needs to be taken into account when developing a project plan.

3.4. Conclusions

Lessons learned from the experience of Visegrad countries are:

1. Public-private partnerships are a key to success in digitizing local services. It is for certain, that setting-up ICT departments for maintenance and especially the development of new ICT tools, in every public authority, is not feasible.
2. Interoperability remains a condition for digitization of local public services, this task being, most certainly, the responsibility of central authorities, which should develop and publish interoperability standards.
3. Digital technologies are progressing, which could repel less knowledgeable citizens. In order to ensure universal access to local digital services it is necessary to develop/purchase ICT tools, independent of certain manufacturers of digital equipment and technology, as well as to implement life-long learning programs for potential applicants of digitized local public services.
4. The digitization of local public services has a social and economic impact only when any of the services can be accessed from any public authority and are provided in a uniform manner.
5. A key role in facilitating universal access to digital services is implementing common means of identification and authentication of users, regardless of the access point and specific public authority.
6. The digitization of public services can be performed only after their successful reengineering. In many cases, preserving existing technological schemes for the delivery of local public services remains a major obstacle to achieve efficient services and ensure universal access.
7. The change of attitude and mentality of the citizens towards the way of providing local public services based on their digitization should be a task, as important as equipping public authorities with ICT tools for electronic provision of the services.

4. Analysis of the workshop participants' output

Problems/Challenges of local e-services implementation
➤ Human factor - the lack of IT specialists (low salaries)
➤ The lack of motivation
➤ Reticence to change, indifference
➤ The citizens are not informed enough, not ready/ not trained
➤ Political will

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The lack of developed equipment, weak internet connection in rural space ➤ Regulatory framework and legislation implementation (the necessity of good implementation mechanisms) ➤ Financial management - not good enough ➤ Underdeveloped infrastructure ➤ The lack/ insufficiency of digital content
Tasks - Topics for discussions in groups
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The most relevant local e-services (you think should be implemented) 2. First 7 steps for implementing local e-services 3. Minimum 2 questions for V4 experts
Group nr.1
<p><u>E-services</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Decisional transparency ➤ Certificate of family composition ➤ Notice of taxes payment ➤ Certificate about place of residence ➤ Cadastral Excerpts ➤ Certificate of possession / landless agricultural <p><i>Steps for e-services implementation:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Study of services identification (services reengineering) 2. Identifying consulting service providers 3. Identification of financial resources 4. Identification of potential partners 5. Pilot project 6. Information, promotion, training 7. Dissemination of good practice <p><i>Questions for V4 specialists</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What was the Impact (%) of the Inclusion Programme (Poland) dr Krzysztof A. 2. For Mr. D. Vratislav - who monitored the accuracy of the Cadastre Register?
Group nr.2
<p><u>E-services</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Social Assistance ➤ Cadastral Services ➤ Archive services ➤ National Social Insurance House ➤ Architect Services ➤ Municipal housing ➤ Public services: Water, heating etc. ➤ Taxes on property <p><i>Steps for e-services implementation:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop action plan based on the existing regulatory framework 2. Consultation the plan with the public-civil society/citizens 3. Identification of financial resources for implementation 4. Creating the database 5. Networking (information system between Local Authorities of I level-villages/cities with Local Authorities of II level-rayons/districts) 6. Training of specialists and awareness of direct beneficiaries 7. Monitoring system functionality

<p><i>Questions for V4 specialists</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What was the biggest problem faced in the implementation process? 2. How did you motivate citizens to access online services?
<p style="text-align: center;">Group nr.3</p> <p><u>E-services</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Cadastre ➤ Social Assistance ➤ Transparent petition process ➤ Civil Status Services ➤ Architecture and urban planning ➤ Small business ➤ Education and health <p><i>Steps for e-services implementation:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The normative base/framework 2. Training of specialists 3. Informing the population 4. Finance 5. Logistics 6. Monitoring 7. Control
<p style="text-align: center;">Group nr.4</p> <p><u>E-services</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Cadastral Services <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.1. Extract from the property Register 1.2. Building permit/authorisation ➤ Petitions (with tracking) ➤ Stop shop ➤ Civil Status Services ➤ Requesting and issuing certificates of tax ➤ Issuing certificates, digitization of data on family composition <p><i>Steps</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Creation of the Local Coordinating e-transformation Council 2. Identify mechanisms and implementation tools 3. Equipment for the Provision and permission to contact via web

Q/A

1. For Mr. D. Vratilav - who monitored the accuracy of the Cadastre Register?

There are three levels of accuracy of maps in the Cadastre Register in Czech Republic.

1. The scanned paper cards with the subsequent preservation on memory devices - the smallest accuracy.
2. Images obtained by scanning with attached digital co-ordinates - average accuracy.
3. Cards obtained by air photography with the attached digital co-ordinates – the highest accuracy.

Air photography is carried out every two years - it ensures accuracy not only of the cadastral maps. All works, including monitoring of the accuracy, are performed by the State Administration of Land Surveying and Cadastre (<http://www.cuzk.cz>).

2. What was the biggest problem faced in the implementation process?

Insufficiently developed methodical decision of the introduced e-service, which always leads to costs, superfluous expenses of the introduced service.

3. How did you motivate citizens to access online services?

In Czech Republic the special advertising campaign for use of e-services has not been organized. Services provided via electronic means, were introduced step-by-step. The crucial importance in use of e-services by the population consisted in their rational force, i.e. **essential** decrease in expenses, availability, the number of services and the speed a particular problem of the citizen was solved.

Example: Information System of Data Boxes, in operation from 1.07.2009, number of established Data Boxes: 647 025, average number of sent off messages per day: 1.700 000. For comparison you can compute expenses on mailing of 1.700 000 sheets of A4 papers across the whole Moldova by mail.

Conclusions

Analysis of the workshop results leads to the following conclusions:

1. In the Republic of Moldova the process of local public services digitization is at the initial stage, the few existing attempts, refer mostly to the use of ICT for disseminating information, pertaining to the activity of local public administration and informing citizens.
2. One of the priorities in the digitization of local public services should be their prioritization depending on the level of demand and identification of those public services, which when digitised would have significant social and economic effects.
3. It is necessary to perform a detailed inventory and a clear delineation of public services provided by local authorities and those provided by the central government, when the local authority only plays the role of agent/operator providing the service.
4. A unique public policy is needed for digitizing local public services. This policy should address all aspects of this process: normative-legal, institutional, technical, organizational.
5. The digitization of local public services should be started with the digitization of all processes within local authorities themselves.
6. Digitisation of local public services requires standard technological solutions. The development of such technological solutions is the responsibility of the central government.

5. Recommendations on implementation of relevant information systems for local authorities

5.1. Czech Republic recommendations

In part 4.1 we described development of IS of public administration with IS of e-services in the Czech Republic. This goal was achieved in 32 years, from 1980 to 2012. There were launches and falling, successes were replaced with failures. Based on this experience, we can assert the following:

- Rationalisation of information systems of the Public Administration is a necessary condition for increase of efficiency of information in a management system of the state.
- Development strategy of the systems of Public Administration must be founded on the philosophy of the solution.
- It is always necessary to take into consideration that the use of electronic services is closely connected with economic and financial systems i.e. there are expenses on operation of electronic services and payments for use of electronic services can be collected.

The above statements may be considered axioms.

Important: The political will and force (to push through the government, parliament) is necessary for working out and introducing information systems of public administration.

After that, the solving of technical problems can be initiated, concerning the following:

- Substantiation of need
- Methodology – base of solutions
- Find instruments (tools) on assertion
- Legislation – laws, regulations, acts, standards, terminology...
- Viability of legislative requirements
- Scaling – central, branch, region, organization
- Work with extents from – to
- Competency – personal, institutional
- Control of abundance
- Development of SW
- Unification of data, distribution of data elements
- Creation of data connectivity
- Linking of subsystems
- Progress
- Not repeating errors of others

5.2. Poland recommendations

Local authorities should consider developing the following types of Information Systems:

1. Basic Internet services
2. Document Management System
3. GIS systems
4. Citizen portal

1) Basic Internet services

The most important thing to start with is to build basic Internet functionality into the local authorities. This step is necessary for the people to know that the local authorities have gone digital. See section 9.

2) Document Management System

After implementation of basic services the number of different documents will subsequently rise. As long as there are few electronic documents, one can rely on ordinary e-mail service. At some point however the volume of information will be too big for ordinary e-mails. In this situation Document Management System should be implemented. The example of such a system is SIGEDIA used in governmental institutions as a Cloud Service (SaaS). Using such a system requires proper infrastructure like scanners. It is very important to combine both electronic and paper documents, as there always be some kind of paper documents (for instance construction plans).

The big question to ask is what system should be implemented and what should be the model of such implementation. If the first step is conducted properly we shall have almost all workflow and document flow ready for implementation, as all the procedures will be written down and optimized.

3) GIS systems

The very important task is to build a comprehensive GIS system. The system should be able to answer several questions about the infrastructure and the environment instantly. It is very useful to have a proper data base of object in each community like roads, traffic signs, buildings etc. It is also important to store information about possible threats: areas likely to be flooded, gas stations, warehouses that store potentially dangerous substances. Of course the information about plots and houses should comprise the land registers numbers and owners data.

The example of such a portal is here:

<http://geoportal.powiat.bielsko.pl/pls/apex/f?p=MAPA:110:4471389526859565:::>

The very important question about such portals is their relation to the countrywide portals. Generally speaking the data stored locally and centrally should be consistent and integrated. That is the theory. In fact there will be always the problem of inconsistency. Entries to the central database usually take longer time to fill in. Secondly there is always a possibility of mistake.

The solution of such a problem is to store both information stored locally and centrally. The elimination of possible inconsistencies is a big task – though it is important to stress that we cannot judge from the start which data is true. At some point in the future all data should be consistent – up to this point it is better to use the IS as a tool to reconcile data than to make too rapid assumptions.

4) Citizen portal

The last proposed system is a citizen portal. This system should be aimed at providing all the necessary information and e-services to the community without the need to send information by traditional mail. The proposed functionality should comprise:

1. Local taxes and fees,
2. Car registration,
3. Waste management,
4. Water and sewage management.

The portal should provide the personalized information to their users. It should also be integrated with the mPay service. The users will be informed by e-mail or SMS about important news. The business goal of such a service is to reduce cost and organizational overhead.

Let us take into a consideration the exemplary community of Ialoveni (population 100700 according to National Bureau of Statistics of the Republic of Moldova.). Let us assume, that this number refers to 25 000 households. Let us also assume that on average each household receives four registered letters annually (one on local taxes and fees, one on car registration, one on waste management and one on water and sewage management).

This gives us some 100 000 letters sent every year. Let us assume that the cost of one letter is 10 lei (4 lei stamp, envelope, cost of printing, handling etc.). Then the cost of operations described above equal to 1 000 000 lei! (0.5% of budget).

Let us assume that only 1/3 of household shall use this system. This gives us savings of 300 000 lei annually, and 3 000 000 lei in ten years.

Of course putting more services into the portal and increase in the users rate shall make this idea even more profitable.

5.3. Slovakia recommendations

Based on the experience on building information systems for e-Government in Slovakia, the following recommendations can be made:

- **Central e-Gov portal** and secondary sectorial portals, interconnected with the central portal
- **Identification of Services** for persons – electronic ID card, e-Signature, common authentication services etc., and to include relationships of persons to company positions, where relevant.
- **e-Communication services** (e.g. e-Boxes) used for guaranteed e-Communication of persons from governmental level and clients' level, including guaranteed electronic delivery.

The components named above are equally important both for central and local e-Services.

5.4. Consolidated recommendations

The issues identified within workshop, confirmed by recent UNDP project Study (2014), supported by **Briefing book from Development Partners for Moldova** (extract attached-Annex 2), based on workshop discussion, V4 countries experience (see Table 1) and local expertise, the following **recommendations on implementation of relevant information systems for local authorities** are proposed.

1. The most relevant solution could be the creation in every Local Public Authority at rayon level, of a Citizen Information and Service Center (CISC) developed within the USAID Local Government Support Project (LGSP). (The Concept of Citizen Information and Service Center attached).

2. For the CISC functionality the Integrated information system of the mayor's office shall be developed.

3. The Integrated information System of the mayor's office will be based on the Electronic Registry of Local Services (ERLS) and the System for Issuing Permissive Documents (SIPD). The IRLS and SIPD will operate on the M-Cloud platform provided by the [E-Government Center](#).

Table 1. Identified issues and possible ICT based solutions for local services							
Main issues identified within workshop	UNDP JILDP identified issues	USAID LGSP identified issues	Briefing book from Development Partners	Czech relevant solution/ recommendation	Polish relevant solution/ recommendation	Slovak relevant solution	USAID LGSP solution
Certificates issuing (family composition, etc.)	Lack of digitalized registers	Services are provided in different locations (offices, floors), in the LPA premise, which fact makes it difficult for the citizens to immediately find the person(s) providing the given service(s); □ Insufficient information about the procedure for service provision, relevant regulations, list of documents requested, terms of execution, etc.; □ Regardless of the fact that there are one-stop shops within LPAs, the applicants submit a set of required documents which	Bring e-Transformation to the level of local government: this will be improving government transactions : both Government to-Go-vernment and Government-to-Citizen.	System of the Shared Services in the Czech Republic which called EGON. EGON consist of: • Communications infrastructure including CMS (central interconnect) • Basic registers: (People, Companies, Land and Houses, Rights a Duties) • Databoxes • CzechPOINT • Governmental portal • List of OVM (Register of offices) • JIP/KAAS – unified identity space for public servants This system is intended to providing of electronics services on regional and local	Development of e-Services needs to be done step by step. The goal of the first step should be: 1.Let people know that they may contact office via internet and encourage them to use. 2.Test the organisations capability in the small scale. Local authorities should consider developing the following types of Information Systems: 1.Basic Internet services, 2.Document Management System, 3.GIS systems, Citizen portal. The first approach to public e-services: Identify stakeholders that could be interested in going digital. Enable possibility to send applications via e-mail without the need to get to	Develop e-Services: • based on your competencies • based on your original data • make links to original sources for other relevant data • without duplication of central Gov work • based on life situation of client – but complex to cover the whole process • use interpretation on maps (GIS or Google maps) Make coalition of local authorities: • by developing and sharing applications	Citizen Information and Service Center (CISC): Integrated information system of the mayor’s office will be based on the Electronic Registry of Local Services (ERLS) and the System for Issuing Permissive Documents (SIPD). The IRLS and SIPD will operate on the M-Cloud platform provided by the E-
Archive services / lack of record keeping of services	Lack of digitalized registers						
Cadastral Excerpts (building permits, excerpts from property register, etc.)	Lack of interoperability						
Certificates on Tax debts	Lack of access to relevant information source						
Social Insurance							
Services are provided in different offices/no one stop-shop office	Lack of information systems for LPA and interoperability between decentralised services Lack of on-line/off-line						

	<p>communication between different public servants from different institutions</p>	<p>is attached to the request by physically showing up at the mayor's office. The request for services in remote mode (via internet, telephone, fax) is not possible; <input type="checkbox"/> LPAs cannot provide service in remote mode, the physical presence of the applicant at the mayor's office is required.</p>		<p>levels. Regional services: - Regional networks interconnect - Regional shared services centers - Public services digital map - Document management. Local services: - Statutory cities shared services centers - Cities shared services centers - Czechpoints front offices - Public services digital map - Document management</p>	<p>the office personally. Implement procedures that trigger right action on the side of the authority upon the receipt of the application. The resulting service might be delivered via traditional mail. Implement PKI structure so that signed applications may be treated as written ones. Identify all the procedures in the office and describe them formally – publish them on the web, along with electronic version of the forms so that people could learn how to deal with their case. Transfer all the forms used in the office to active pdf (you may use tools like Scribus).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (sharing of expenditures) • Think for structure of your e-Services • the client would be not lost Take care on administrative burden !! • don't ask for data which are in Gov databases • assess the real usage of all collected data in time • cancel obligations of clients when are different ways to collect data 	<p>Government Center.</p>
<p>Lack of networking (IS) between rayons (LPAII) and villages (LPAI)</p>							
<p>Decisional transparency/ lack of information</p>							<p>LPA Webpage</p>

According to the Concept CISC shall be implemented within the LPA in 2 stages:

□ In the 1st implementation stage, before developing the ERLS and SIPD, CISC will perform the function of interaction between the citizens and the mayor's office, while the management of information and documents will be done in hard copy manually. All the requests and sets of documents will be submitted to CISC, recorded in the common registry of in-coming documents, and then submitted to the Mayor for examination and designation of persons responsible for their execution.

□ In the 2nd stage, the entire circuit of information and documents will be insured in electronic form. In the 2nd stage, after the implementation of the Electronic Registry of Local Services (ERLS) and of the System for Issuing Permissive Documents (SIPD), provided by Government through the [e-Government Center](#) (which will serve as a basis for the integrated information system of the mayor's office), the management and circulation of documents will take place in electronic form.

These systems will cover the entire circulation cycle of documents and information, starting with filing requests for obtaining services, for service provision, documents' circulation both within the mayor's office and de-concentrated services through communication and information exchange and finishing with the archiving of documents.

Clients will be able to pay through the payment terminal installed in the premise of CISC, which will be connected to the ERLS.

However, to ensure the functionality of CISC, a range of additional actions have to be planned and implemented.

To be noted from Czech experience:

Successful creation and introduction of Information System of Public Administration (ISPA) at local level (region, district) is not possible without:

1. Creations of the legislative and normative uniform environment for all ISPA.
2. Creation of the Information system about data elements for:
 - working out not only of all ISPA,
 - creations of condition for integrability of ISPA at all levels of PA.
3. Creation of a methodology for every ISPA, as base for software development.
 - Rationalisation of information systems of the Public Administration is a necessary condition for increase of efficiency of information in a management system of the state.
 - Development strategy of the systems of Public Administration must be founded on the philosophy of solution.
 - It is always necessary to take into consideration that the use of electronic services is closely connected with economic and a financial system i.e. there are expenses on operation of electronic services and payments for use of electronic services can be collected.

For working out IS for providing of e-services at local level it is necessary to have the data minimum from two IS of public administration - the Register of Inhabitants and IS subject domain i.e. from which it is necessary to provide service.

After solving these problems it is possible to start to own working out of the project on providing of service in the form of e-service, maintenance of its documenting, economy connected with providing of the service, infrastructure and other technical problems.

Based on the above, it is necessary to conduct (at least) the following steps:

1. Implementation of the electronic documents circulation
2. Information system about Data Elements
3. Collection, summarization of the economical data
4. Simple e-Services

To be noted from Slovak experience:

Changing of processes

- Systematic approach
- People / Stakeholders
- coordinated

- cooperated
- motivated
- User friendly approach supporting various endusers' equipments
- Awareness and Trainings
- to Gov
- to Companies
- to Citizens
- Thinking on various levels of clients' access
- Support
- Never ending process !!

6. Recommendations on local e-services to be developed

6.1. Czech Republic recommendations

For working out IS for providing of e-services at local level it is necessary to have the data minimum from two IS of public administration - the Register of Inhabitants and IS of subject domain i.e. from which it is necessary to provide service.

Further it is necessary to have means for the authorised conversion of documents, i.e. legal equivalence of documents in an electronic and paper form is provided.

After solving these problems it is possible to start working out of the project on providing of service in the form of e-service, maintenance of its documents, economy connected with providing of the service, infrastructure and other technical problems.

Based on the above, it is necessary to conduct (at least) the following steps::

1. Implementation of the electronics document circulation
2. Information system about Data Elements
3. Collection, summarization of the economical data
4. Simple e-Services

6.2. Poland recommendations

Development of e-Services needs to be done step by step. It is important to stress that implementation of e-services is not really an ICT problem. Moreover, as it was mentioned during the workshop, it is no good to implement perfect – from formal and theoretical points of view – e-Services that would not be used by the people.

The other aspect is economical:

- it is not sensible to do the same thing for each community separately – it is good to implement initial services in 2-3 regions and then roll it out to other locations,
- try to use as much Open Software as possible.

First step

The goal of the first step should be:

1. **Let people know that they may contact office via internet and encourage them to use.**
2. **Test the organisations capability in the small scale.**

The first approach to public e-services should be as following:

1. Identify stakeholders that could be interested in going digital.

It would be quite good to identify stakeholders that would be interested in e-government in the first place. Of course each community will have its own idea. The first guess would be the business people who want their applications to be settled quickly and efficiently. One have to make sure that they are assisted during the first phase of implementing the services. See also section 10.

2. Enable possibility to send applications via e-mail without the need to get to the office personally. Make sure that SPAM configurations are right.

E-mail is very basic service that can really make the difference in community operations. It is very important that every clerk had his/her own e-mail address in community domain and this address should be published on the web.

3. Implement procedures that trigger the right action on the side of the authority upon the receipt of the application. The resulting service might be delivered via traditional mail.

Implementation basic e-mail service requires the implementation of general netiquette. Every person in the office should check their e-mail frequently. Receipt confirmation of an email should be always be provided. The “*out of office*” notices indicating people in charge is also a must.

It is also important that e-mails sent to the general addresses were sent to the right person. The top management of the community should be provided with smartphones so that they can check their mail everywhere. Blackberry service should be considered.

4. Implement PKI structure so that signed applications may be treated as written ones.

The next step is an implementation of PKI in the office. With this service documents sent by mail can be treated as written ones. Usually only few people have a digital signature – this requires a proper document and workflow. Ideally the digitally signed application should be processed and the digitally signed result should be sent this way.

5. Identify all the procedures in the office and describe them formally – publish them on the web, along with electronic version of the forms so that people could learn how to deal with their case.

This task is very important to the future implementation of e-service. All procedures in the office should be written down and described formally so that citizens know what they should do. This could be somewhat similar to <https://servicii.gov.md>, however in many ways more detailed. This task shall take a lot of time. Once the procedures are recognized the optimization phase is necessary. It would be particularly useful if this task is performed in cooperation with other communities. It shall lead to the identification of best practices throughout Moldova.

6. Transfer all the forms used in the office to active .pdf (you may use tools like Scribus).

It is very useful to implement all the forms of pdf, so that everybody could download needed document and fill it electronically (even if it is printed).

Please check the good example: http://www.mfa.gov.md/img/docs/Visa_application.pdf

7. Register profile on Twitter, Facebook, Google+ and publish important information there.

Media like Facebook, Google+ and Twitter are more and more popular, especially among young people. In many cases there are already ready to use profiles like <https://www.facebook.com/pages/Ialoveni/111871995496215?fref=ts>

Such profiles enable more interactive communication with the people. In some cases they may be treated as emergency form of communications. Good example: <http://www.il.md>

8. Implement helpdesk for the people, possibly with the use of Skype.

Implementing a helpdesk is a must – the people should always be able to ask a living person for advise. It is useful to utilize popular media like skype for the task. Goal of such an approach is also to gain interest in internet version of the office.

9. Provide information on new approach by attaching leaflet to each mail. Print posters and put them in the office.

Promotion of any activity is a necessary part of each plan. Leaflets attached to official mails, posters, promotional information in local newspapers are the most important means of communications. It is essential however that the web site should be functional to some extent. Promotion out of date service is not a good idea.

10. Implement public internet access and install a few computers in the premises, so that people may use it.

The last element of the plan is quite obvious. Usually it does not take much effort to provide public WiFi in the office and few computers for people to use. This action has also a

promotional factor – people see that there are computers in use and the office can be contacted by internet.

Most of those actions could be done without much investment. I would not expect that people will rush to their screens to send applications. This is actually a good thing because it shall enable organisation to go digital without much risk of a blunder.

6.3. Slovakia recommendations

In previous chapters, both experiences and good practices with information systems and partially with eServices development were shared. But,

what is e-Service?

‘The provision of electronic services via the Internet ...’

*‘The **online services available on the Internet**, whereby a valid transaction of buying and selling (procurement) is possible, as opposed to the traditional **websites**, whereby only **descriptive information** are available, and no online transaction is made possible.’*

Wikipedia both

*“**Interface** between the person from government and the end user to fulfill his/her needs or obligations electronically, without visiting the Governmental office and in optional time.”*

Personal interpretation

From this definition it is clear, there is no need to speak separately about information systems and e-Services. Both are about the same and one without another will not fully fulfil client’s needs – when speaking about rules, conditions, operation, functionalities. Therefore when building good e-Services, it is necessary to respect the rules and recommendations written before.

Instead of additional words, the information is on the picture:

Important points for e-Services (Services)

What is important for **GOOD e-Services**

- **Plan / Feasibility Study / Implementation**

- owner of process, client
- safety
- data, architecture, broadband, development, testing
- legislation
- agreements, procurements
- neighbourhood – interoperability – SOA
- timetable, management, maintenance
- sources
- awareness, trainings
- user friendly approach, helpdesk, clients’ centers
- sustainability – loop: assessment, updates, change management

One-Stop-Shop:

- **save money**
- **save time**
- **execute 24/7**

... and “**Change the administrative processes**” before starting to develop IS/e-Service !!

7. The main steps to be included into the Action plan for implementation of local e-services rural localities

7.1. Czech Republic

Before starting the implementation of local e-services in rural localities it is necessary to calculate the expenses and then to search for the approach to their introduction.

7.2. Poland

Building viable Information Systems is a step by step process which must include various aspects: technological, social, theoretical etc. It is strongly recommended to use the TOGAF (The Open Group Architectural Framework) approach, which proved to be very effective in many cases including Government of United States. Presentation of the framework itself is out of the scope of this document. One may easily obtain relevant information at <https://www.opengroup.org/togaf/>.

The basic concept of TOGAF is ADM (Architecture Development Method).

It is quite important to stress that TOGAF is not the “methodology” i.e. each application needs to be adjusted to the specific case.

The following steps is form proposed simplification of ADM.

1. Identify stakeholders on implementing information systems: government ministries, business entities, public officers etc.
2. Assess the impact on the systems for each stakeholder: some stakeholders are important, some may be neglected.
3. Identify stakeholders sorrows: for instance public officers may be afraid that automation of the services shall result for the them to lose their jobs.

4. Establish governing board and project owner.
5. Describe baseline architecture:
 - a. Procedures,
 - b. Existing databases,
 - c. Existing applications,
 - d. Existing technical infrastructure.
6. Identify existing constraints:
 - a. Organisational,
 - b. Technical,
 - c. Legal,
 - d. Financial.
7. Design target architecture:
 - a. Affected procedures,
 - b. New databases
 - c. New applications
 - d. New infrastructure.
8. Perform gap analysis and develop implementation plan.
9. Produce required tender documentation and choose supplier(s).
10. Do the project with selected supplier(s).
11. Monitor and control the project including the stakeholder satisfaction:
 - a. Identify possible risks.
 - b. Manage the changes in the project.
12. Close the project:
 - a. Gather necessary documentation.
 - b. Write down lessons learned.
 - c. Identify possible projects in the future.

7.3. Slovakia

When developing local e-Services, it is important to start activities using a bottom-up approach and to **build a plan** on how to do it – taking into account many aspects written in this document – using the following steps:

- **organizing coalition of stakeholders** from local level with knowledge and interest, aiming to identify a single way and save resources;
- formalizing these actions by creating a **Task Force**, which will be the partner for all relevant bodies in the state and all other levels, will coordinate work on local level, communicate with central level, will lead the planning and implementation processes at the local level;
- **communicating with all stakeholders on national level** responsible for e-Transformation, targeting to keep informed about plans from central government (including time schedules and responsibilities) and **asking for building of a common platform**, which could be used for information systems and e-Services of local government (not only HW, but also basic common applications);
- identifying the **common needs** on local level **divided in two groups**: e-Services which can be based on local data and e-Services, which require data from central/national level;
- **influencing central plans** according to the local needs;
- urgently striving to develop **electronic identification of persons**, as the basic assumption for e-Government;

- preparing concrete **Action Plan on building of IS/e-Services for local level** based on actions above;
- **allocating resources** (both human and financial);
- **organizing work to build useful IS and e-Services** for local level, while waiting for certain steps to be taken on central level – start with systematic publishing and continue building e-Service of higher level;
- **organizing events** for representatives of all local governments in the country, to be transparent, open about taking on board all the local governments not yet involved, with interest to participate and for common benefits, thus increasing the Task Force work;
- **explaining the benefits** of the Task Force work to the general public, also **motivating** them to use newly developed e-Services (e.g. via discounts of usual payments etc.)

8. Recommendations on public policies, regulations to be proposed for the discussion on the next event (Seminar) planned for the end of May, 2015 etc. based on V4 best practices and the findings of the workshop

8.1. Czech Republic

We suggest the following theme: The legislation and technical standards in Public Administration

One of the discussion goals should be to conduct inventory of the Moldovan legislation from the point of view of IS of public administration, especially from the point of view of the providing e-services.

During inventory it is necessary to find out gaps which block the use of IT in public administration and establish impacts of gaps in the legislation for the use of IT in public administration.

Further: what laws, regulations are necessary and in which sequence these must be developed and accepted. Finally, what technical standards are necessary to be accepted and introduced.

8.2. Poland

This topic is particularly complex. It would be quite difficult to produce comprehensive results. It is quite important to stress that most regulations require funding. For example, if we introduce regulation that electronic signature must be recognized in all Moldova institutions one has to ask a question who is going to pay for obtaining suitable hardware and software.

Introducing such regulations is also no “one click” act. One has to build a timeline to introduce respective regulations.

Nevertheless what can be done is as follows:

1. Identify areas of regulations that have to be covered (before workshop).
2. Identify existing Republic of Moldova regulations that may coincide (before workshop).
3. Develop plan to build the respective regulations (ideas formulated before the workshop – workshop itself could be focused on developing the plan).

Ad. 1.)

Proposed areas of regulations are:

1. Electronic signature and electronic documents,
2. Personal data protection,
3. Interoperability regulations in public systems,
4. Rules on building IS for public sector:
 - a. financing projects,

- b. minimum requirements for the IS (technological neutrality and transparency standards and specifications),
 - c. public records and exchange of information in electronic form with public entities,
 - d. controlling projects,
 - e. the exchange of information by electronic means, including electronic documents, between public and non-party entities public
 - f. the common electronic platform of public administration,
 - g. central repository of models of electronic documents.
5. User identification in IS;
 6. E-Services regulations,
 7. Public Information regulations.

Ad. 2.)

Having agreed on areas of regulation, we have to find out all existing regulations in Moldova system of law. For instance we have to check what is meant by “document” in civil law, administrative law etc. and consequently change that meaning.

Ad. 3.)

There are at least few options to develop the viable regulations enabling the Information Society development:

- A. Identify best practices around the world and develop custom regulations,
- B. Identify EU regulations and develop Republic of Moldova’s version
- C. Identify Romanian regulations and adopt to Republic of Moldova.

The “A” approach is likely to produce best possible result, however it should take long time to develop – which we do not have. Another drawback is that – taking into an account European option for Republic of Moldova – that such regulation will have to be changed in the future. The regulations developed in South Korea or United States may be quite sensible – but what will happen if they are not compliant with EU regulations? Another drawback is the relatively high cost.

That is why it is quite good to adopt the EU regulations to Moldova (option “B”). Such approach ensures that the regulations are tested throughout EU 28 member states. The EU compatibility is right away. Still one has to bear in mind that producing new bills is a quite long and an expensive process.

The possibly the easiest way to produce quite good result is to look through the regulations made in Romania (option “C”). Even if they are not perfect they are ready. There is not a translation problem. The only questions to be asked are:

- How those regulations alter existing ones?
- What is the cost of implementing such regulations?
- Are there any EU regulations not yet implemented?

This option does not mean that bills have to be 1:1 – they might be some changes needed to ensure proper implementation. Such regulation should be treated as version 1.0 of respective bills – it is quite possible that there will be changes necessary in the future. One has to monitor how this laws works in practice.

Of course the actual implementation could probably be a hybrid of A, B and C options. The choice of the strategy should determine which option is dominant and which is subsidiary.

8.3. Slovakia

The best way is to identify the actual status or plans for adoption of all regulations/laws in the Republic of Moldova which are crucial for e-Government. Many of them are named in this report, many are named in documents adopted by the central government. The knowledge about the practical implementation milestones of respective regulations can be very useful, as it explains when it could be used on the local level (e.g. eID, e-Signature, relevant applications

etc.). Based on the result of this research, the missing stones can be identified during the seminar or later on.

8.4. Consolidated recommendations:

The following discussion topics are recommended for the next event:

The legislation, regulations and technical standards in Public Administration from the point of view of IS of public administration, especially from the point of view of the providing e-services

9. Conclusions

1. The participants from local public authorities to the first DISCUS Project event appreciated the content of presented materials by international and local experts, as well as the productive discussions.

2. To boost the use of ICT for local services development, a practical presentation by e-Governance Centre at the next event explaining the main steps to be done by LPA for use of e-Governance Center Platform for organization of provision of local e-services has to be organised.

3. The DISCUS platform could be widely used to discuss and promote the results obtained in other projects in the field of local services enhancement.

Agenda
Workshop on ICT-driven local development
17-18.03.2015 - Chisinau, Moldova
Labour Institute, Room nr. 4, 10 Zimbrului str., Chisinau, Moldova, 2024

1st Day – March 17th			
Time	nr	Topic/presentation	Speaker/expert/moderator
9.30 - 10.00	Arrival & Registration		
	1	Workshop opening	Anastasia Stefanita, Information Society Development Institute
10.00 - 10.10	1. 1	Opening remarks & overview of the Agenda (Ro)	Igor Cojocaru Director, Information Society Development Institute
10.10 - 10.20	1. 2	Welcome speech (Ro)	Vitalie Tarlev Deputy Minister of Information Technology and Communication
10.20 - 10.30	1. 3	DISCUS Project Presentation (Ro)	Anastasia Stefanita, ISDI Project coordinator
	2	Current situation of the ICT-driven local development in Moldova	Ion Cosuleanu, Information Society Development Institute
10.30 - 10.45	2. 1	A brief introduction on the current situation of the e-Government in Moldova (tbc) (Ro)	eGov Center, Moldova
10.45 - 11.00	2. 2	Presentation of the Study on access and usage prospects of local public services online, Joint Integrated Local Development Programme (Ro)	Olesea Cazacu UNDP Moldova Project coordinator
11.00 - 11.15	2. 3	Local Open Government based on ICT tools (Ro)	Veronica Cretu President, Open Government Institute (Moldova), member of the steering committee of the Open Government Partnership
11.15 - 11.35	2. 4	Issues & Achievements at local level (Study case – Ialoveni, Moldova) (Ro)	Igor Plamadeala, Ialoveni Rayonal Council
11.35 - 12.15	2. 5	Discussions on presented topics during the coffee break	All
	3	ICT-driven local development in V4 countries (good practices)	Ion Cosuleanu, Information Society Development Institute
12.15- 12.50	3. 1	Local e-services - good practices in Poland (Eng)	Krzysztof Atlasiewicz Expert Poland
		Q&A session	
12.50 - 13.25	3. 2	Important system points by building local e-services based on Slovakia practices (Eng)	Vladimir Benko Expert Slovakia
		Q&A session	
13.25 - 14.00	3. 3	Methodological approaches on ICT-driven local development (including e-services) (Eng)	Vratislav Datel Expert Czech Republic
		Q&A session	
14.00 - 14.50	Lunch		
14.50 - 15.20	3. 4	Discussions on V4 best practices. Recommendations for Moldova	Facilitators: Anatol Gremalschi, director Institute for Public Policy

			Ion Cosuleanu, ISDI
	4	Focus groups work	
15.20 - 16.30	4.1	Focus groups work (3 groups*approx. 10 persons) Topics to be identified based on presentations and Q&A sessions	Facilitator: Veronica Cretu President, Open Government Institute (Moldova), member of the steering committee of the Open Government Partnership
16.30 - 17.30	4.2	Presentations of 3 focus groups work results & coffee break	
17.30 - 18.10	4.3	Final discussions & conclusions	Facilitators: Anatol Gremalschi , Program director, Institute for Public Policy Ion Cosuleanu, ISDI
18.10 - 19.30	Networking event		
2nd day – March 18th			
	5	Action plan for local e-services implementation	Mihai Greco , Information Society Development Institute
09.00 - 09.30	5.1	Proposals for development of the Action Plan Draft for local e-services implementation	Vratislav Datel Expert Czech Republic
09.30 – 09.40		Q&A	
09.40 – 10.10	5.2	Recommendations/Useful advices on implementation of relevant information systems for local authorities	Krzysztof Atlasiewicz Expert Poland
10.10 – 10.20		Q&A	
10.20 – 10.35	5.3	Recommendations/Useful advices on implementation of relevant information systems for local authorities	Vladimir Benko Expert Slovakia
10.35 - 10.45		Q&A session	
10.45 - 11.45	Coffee Break & Discussions		
	6	IT Performance Centers - concept	Anatol Gremalschi , Program director, Institute for Public Policy
11.45 - 12.05	6.1	General presentation of IT Performance Centers idea (Look@IT study results)	Ion Cosuleanu, ISDI
12.05 - 12.20	6.2	IT Performance Centers Concept. Issues & possible solutions	Ion Cosuleanu, ISDI
12.35 - 12.50	6.3	Digital content and motivation of youths	Vladimir Benko Expert Slovakia
12.50 - 13.50	6.4	Discussions on IT Performance Centers Concept	Facilitators: Anatol Gremalschi , IPP, Ion Cosuleanu, ISDI
13.50 - 14.50	Lunch		
14.50 - 15.30	Final discussions & conclusions of the event		
15.30 - 16.00	Feedback questionnaire		
16.00 - 17.00	Coffee Break & final organisational issues		
17.00 - 17.30	Wrap-up & Departure		

DISCUS is a project funded under the International Visegrad Fund

<http://visegradfund.org/>

Annex 2: Extract from “Briefing Book from Development Partners”

http://eeas.europa.eu/delegations/moldova/documents/press_corner/briefing_book_final_feb-10-2015-rev_order_en.pdf :

Public Services (Page 13)

Making public services work for the population and firms. Inefficient, fragmented and often corrupt service delivery increases the cost of doing business, harms growth and limits access, especially for poor and rural people. To address this, Moldova has made commitments to simplify and digitize all public services by 2020. With (Government) Resolution no. 661, it decided to scale up the “Single Information and Services Bureau” model. The [e-Government Center](#) has made impressive progress in providing the IT-infrastructure for online services. However, business process reengineering has lagged behind, both at the center and in local government, and is the most important public administration challenge ahead;

Short-term reforms (<12 months): (Page 14)

- Undertake the mid-term review of the Public Services Modernization Program for 2014-2016, identify implementation challenges, and scale-up re-engineering of business processes for priority services, focused on early wins and in close integration with one-stop shops /digitization of services;
- Develop the model and action plan for implementing service delivery centers, based on onestop shop approach, for public services at all levels of the government; and
- Undertake functional reorganization and change management in agencies based on reengineered public services and support results-oriented management.

Medium-term reforms (>12 months): (Page 15)

- Systematically reengineer and digitize priority services across central and local government agencies, and make them accessible through one-stop shops to firms and population; and
- Public Services: Establish a system for monitoring customer satisfaction with public services. (Pag.19-20)

To benefit from these infrastructure investments (in e-Government Centre & CTS), the Government will need to show strong political leadership. This means enforcing the mandatory use of existing infrastructure and e-government platforms by sectorial ministries and completing establishment of the MCloud Phase II facility. **The next challenge will be to extend the infrastructure and services to the level of local government and constituents.**

Short-term recommendations (<100 days):

- Mandate through a Government decision that no business process or public service should be digitized, unless it has been streamlined and simplified;
- Complete procurement of MCloud Phase II facility; and
- Closely align public sector reforms with the e-Transformation agenda and consider reengineering governance and current institutional arrangement for Information Technology management. Specifically:
 - Set up the Public Service Reform Task Force chaired by Prime Minister, comprising State Chancellery, Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Justice to coordinate and provide leadership in driving and enforcing the public sector and public service modernization agenda;
 - Set up the ICT Governance Board, comprising Ministry of Finance, State Chancellery, [e-Government Center](#), [Ministry of ICT](#), Public Procurement Agency to coordinate the public ICT investments to support Government Reform and Modernization. The Board would be responsible for ensuring reuse of existing e-Government Infrastructure and smart investments in IT in government;
 - Set up Public Service Design and Innovation Unit under the Prime Minister’s Office to drive and deliver modernization of public service through innovation-based transformation and digitization of public services all across the government;

- Synchronize Public Service Reform at central and local government levels (e.g., Decentralization Reform, specifically related to public service delivery, and Public Service Reform Agenda);
- Approve and enforce the Smart IT Investment Framework to guide and ensure smart investments in ICT by ministries and government agencies; and
- Set up Cyber Security Government Task Force to ensure coordination and implementation all across government of priority measures to ensure secure digital government.

Medium-term recommendations (< 12 months):

- Issue a Government Decree allowing government data to be used by the private sector, academia, and local government – especially data which are currently sold for a fee. This will foster innovation and technological breakthroughs in developing user-friendly services;
- Finalize draft amendments on asset declaration and submit to Parliament. The draft amendment should include provisions allowing for electronic filing of declarations, use of electronic signature and making e-signature available to the filers;
- Synchronize Technological/Digital Modernization with enacting new supporting policy decisions and legislation. The “20th century” legal and policy framework is often holding back innovation and technology adoption in government. Specifically, the following legal and policy actions would need to be undertaken:
 - Approve the Law on Public Services and e-Government, to support innovation and technology adoption in government in line with the EU Digital Agenda 2020, EU eGovernment Agenda, Open Data Strategy and Cloud Computing Strategy;
 - Approve Policy Decisions and Regulations to enable the data exchange and interoperability through Government Platform MConnect, and to enforce the “Only Once” Principle of Data submission by the population and businesses to government. Align Moldova Legal Framework with the EU Framework of Interoperability of PanEuropean Public Service Delivery;
 - Ensure personal data protection, as well as align relevant legislation with EU standards, and implement it effectively; and
 - Approve and enforce cyber security policy, regulations and implementation mechanisms to ensure secure digital communication, interactions, and transactions between people, businesses and government in Moldova and in the EU Digital Market;
- Replace the current Information Technology (IT) investment/procurement arrangements with a framework which encourages the sharing of e-government platforms between departments. This would make it easier to cover the cost of IT modernization. Government may consider setting up a Smart IT Investment Board, where Ministry of Finance, Agency of Public Procurement, State Chancellery, [e-Government Center](#)/CIO Office of the Government and [Ministry of Information Technology and Communications](#) could decide on a coordinated IT budget and procurement program to ensure value for money.

Long-term recommendations (>12 months):

- Increase population’s digital literacy: this is important to increase the uptake of government e-services and platforms; and
- Bring e-Transformation to the level of local government: this will be improving government transactions: both Government-to-Government and Government-to-Citizen.

Research Study “Administrative public services at local level: diagnostic and e-transformation opportunities” UNDP Moldova, 2014

Most commonly, people are addressed to the municipality for: certificate of family composition, certificate required in several contexts (at work, in educational institutions, in order to receive some relief or welfare, material etc.). Other certificates are often required on: lack of debts to the local budget and certificates of possession or lack of agricultural land.

Citizens are mostly addressing for: notary certificates, certificates on property, and in some places, where there are problems with land titles, citizens are addressing the cadastral engineer to acquire those certificates.